

Photon Wave Equation from Continuity Equation with Poynting Vector Part II

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In Part I of this note, we argued that a quantum mechanical photon wave equation follows from a sourceless continuity equation including the Poynting vector i.e. $\frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = 0$ ($c=1$). In other words, if one factors $(\mathbf{E} - i\mathbf{B})$ from this equation for general linearly polarized light, $\mathbf{E} = (\cos(a), \sin(b), 0) \exp(i(kx - \omega t))$ $k=\omega$, one obtains a photon wave equation. Then: $\frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{E} - i\mathbf{B})(\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) = (\mathbf{E} - i\mathbf{B}) \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B})$ and one has: $i \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) = (\mathbf{S} \cdot (-i \text{grad})) (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B})$ where $S_i = \epsilon_{ijk}$. The derivation follows for generally linearized light, but one may take linear combinations to form circularly polarized light.

In this note, we argue that the physical ideas of photon spin seem to follow from the Poynting vector $\frac{1}{\mu_0} \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ with \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} perpendicular to the photon motion. \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are perpendicular so one has many degenerate solutions, with \mathbf{E} at a different angle in the x - y plane. These degenerate solutions have the same momentum and energy and one may form a linear combination $\mathbf{E} = (\cos(kx - \omega t), -\sin(kx - \omega t), 0)$. Given that $\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$ represents energy (and a similar result for \mathbf{B}), one has physical circular motion or angular motion about z which does not change the overall momentum or energy. (Similar results hold for the x and y axes.) This differs from a classical particle for which $p = mv$, but energy = $\frac{1}{2} m v^2 + \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2$. Thus, we argue that it is the degeneracy in the position of \mathbf{E} in the Poynting vector which gives rise to a photon's spin. For S_x , S_y and S_z one has the same (or very similar) rotational pattern about the i (from S_i) axis. Thus, even in the more general case of a non- z direction, there is physical rotation about each x axis of \mathbf{E} components perpendicular to that axis. This seems to differ from the Pauli matrices which appear in an electron in the Dirac treatment.

Recap of Procedure to Obtain Photon Wave Equation

The photon wave function may be obtained from the energy-Poynting vector continuity equation with no sources. We choose this equation because it contains physical quantities associated with a photon namely energy and momentum density.

$$\epsilon_0 \frac{d}{dt} (\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \epsilon_0 \text{grad} \cdot (\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{We write: } \frac{d}{dt} (\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) = (\mathbf{E} - i\mathbf{B})(\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}) \quad ((2))$$

This holds for generally linearized light i.e. $\mathbf{E} = (\cos(a), \sin(a), 0) \cos(k(z-t))$ motion in the z direction. Then, we argue that $\text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{E} - i\mathbf{B}) \cdot (\mathbf{S} \cdot -\text{grad}) (\mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B})$ where $S_i(jk) = \epsilon_{ijk}$. The Levi-Civita symbol is anti-symmetric in any two indices ϵ_{ijk} while $\epsilon_{l di} \epsilon_{m}$ (where $d_i = d/dx_i$) is symmetric in l and m so only \mathbf{E} with $\text{grad} \mathbf{B}$ or \mathbf{B} with $\text{grad} \mathbf{E}$ survive. See Part I for the full derivation.

The derivation is performed for generally linearized light. Later, one may take linear combinations to produce circular polarized light $\mathbf{E} = (\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0)$. In this case $\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) = \text{a constant}$.

Angular Momentum and the Poynting Vector

We have chosen to derive the photon wave function from a continuity equation including the Poynting vector because we argue that this vector is important in determining the nature of photon spin. First, a photon satisfies $E^2 = p^2 c^2$ where E is energy and p momentum. There are no E and B fields in this equation, it is simply a relationship between energy and momentum $E=pc$. If one examines details, there is in fact an E and B field, but they are constrained for a photon to motion related to $E=pc$ i.e. $\exp(ipx - iEnt)$ appears in expressions for E and B . The Poynting vector $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ may be integrated to give the value of momentum. $\text{Grad} \cdot 1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ gives the energy flowing out of a surface. E and B are perpendicular to the motion of the photon and energy and have the same magnitude.

Thus, there are many degenerate E values. In fact, one may choose any E vector from the origin in an xy plane if the photon motion is in the z direction. These have the same momentum and energy values, but for a circularly polarized photon, E i.e. $(\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0)$ yields an E which circles in time, but has a constant magnitude i.e. energy. Thus with B , overall energy and momentum do not change even though there is angular momentum. This angular momentum is argued to be the photon spin (1). Thus, it is by examining details of the momentum density (Poynting vector) that one finds angular momentum which is spin at least in the photon case.

For a classical particle, rotational energy does not change momentum mv , but it does change overall energy $mv^2 + \frac{1}{2} I \omega^2$.

The matrices $S = i \epsilon_{ijk}$ are 3×3 , but have very similar 2×2 behaviour for each axis i.e.

Photon moves along x $S_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ rotation of E_y and E_z ((3a))

Photon moves along y $S_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & i \\ -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ rotation of E_x, E_z ((3b))

Photon moves along z $S_z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ rotation of E_x, E_y ((3c))

Physically, there does not seem to be any difference in moving in one direction versus another as the spin is physical rotation about the axis of motion.

Such is not the case for an electron in the Dirac treatment, or for the Pauli nonrelativistic treatment of the electron interacting with a magnetic field. In such a case, the matrices are:

$S_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ $S_y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ $S_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$ ((4 a,b,c))

These are unitary and Hermitian and related to the generators of the SU2 group. These are part of Dirac's 4x4 matrices which act on the top spinor of the 4-vector. They are like the Levi-Civita matrices for the EM case. Unlike the EM case, however, the electron spin (or the Pauli matrices) seem to be introduced through mathematics. In this note, we try to argue that in the EM case one may see some of the physics through the Poynting vector. The analogy seems to carry over to an extent in the Dirac case where current is given by $W^* \mu W$ (3) where μ is the μ th Dirac matrix (containing a Pauli matrix), but this current is linked to $d/dt W^* W$ not energy density as in the EM case.

Spin supplies details related to unitary transformations in an equation linear in both derivatives and (E and B) in the EM case, but disappears in the Klein-Gordon equation, indicating that spin does not change the energy of a photon. A similar result holds for a free particle unless it interacts (say an electron spin with a magnetic field). The formalism of the EM case with spin 1 and the electron case with spin $1/2$ are similar.

The Pauli equation (2) for a nonrelativistic electron interacting with a magnetic field is:

$$\{1/2m (p-qA) \cdot (p-qA) + q \phi - q \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}\} W = i\hbar d/dt W \quad ((5))$$

If B is zero, spin does not appear. Thus, an electron has energy and momentum and spin, but without an external B field, there is no change to the electron energy in ((5)) due to spin. Thus, $E_n E_n = p p + m m$. This is similar to the photon case where there is a spin of 1 which does not change energy or momentum i.e. $E_n E_n = p p$. Both are different from classical spinning or rotation which does increase rest energy. (In some models of zitterbewegung, the electron is described as traveling in helical motion which represents physical angular momentum creating spin.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we reiterate that the photon wave function may be obtained from the EM continuity equation including the Poynting vector. We consider a generalized linearly polarized E field to do this. Some physics seems to follow from the Poynting vector which allows for many degenerate E,B orientations in an xy plane for a photon moving in the z. Each solution has the same momentum and energy and the S matrix (in $i d/dt (E+iB) = (\mathbf{S} \cdot -\text{grad}) (E+iB)$) is $i \epsilon_{ijk}$ where ϵ_{ijk} is the Levi-Civita symbol which follows directly from the Poynting vector $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$. If one forms circularly polarized light, it has energy and momentum which are unaffected in value by the angular momentum (spin). ϵ_{ijk} has the same (or nearly the same) rotational behaviour in x,y,z directions showing a rotational behaviour perpendicular to the direction of motion.

The form of the photon wave function is very similar to the Dirac equation of an electron. In such a case, however, spin must arise which couples with a magnetic field. The spin energy is $\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ where S_i are matrices very similar to the generators of the SU2 group. (They are made Hermitian and unitary.) Like in the EM case, these appear in the Dirac treatment directly in a linear quantum equation which must also convert to the Klein-Gordon equation linking energy

and momentum without any spin present (because it does affect energy or momentum of a free particle).

References

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